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THE ECONOMIC NATURE OF LOCAL FINANCE AND THE DETERMINATION OF ITS SOCIAL ROLE UNDER THE TRANSFORMATION OF UKRAINE'S PUBLIC FINANCE SYSTEM

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Анотація. У статті досліджено економічну природу місцевих фінансів та визначено їхню соціальну роль в умовах трансформації системи публічних фінансів України. Здійснено аналіз історичної еволюції місцевих фінансів у зарубіжному та вітчизняному контекстах, у результаті якого виявлено перехід від трактування місцевих фінансів як простого кошторису видатків громади до усвідомлення їх як складного інструменту забезпечення життєздатності територій і фінансової самостійності. Обґрунтовано, що якщо в зарубіжних країнах розвиток місцевих фінансів відбувався еволюційним шляхом до розширення автономії, то український досвід тривалий час характеризувався високим рівнем централізації в межах адміністративно-командної системи, подолання якої нині здійснюється через процеси фіскальної децентралізації.

У роботі систематизовано наукові підходи до визначення поняття «місцеві фінанси» за п'ятьма групами: системно-ресурсний, функціональний, економічний, соціально-економічний та правовий. Така класифікація засвідчує багатовимірний характер місцевих фінансів як складової публічних фінансів і водночас фінансової основи місцевого самоврядування. Запропоновано уточнене авторське визначення місцевих фінансів як інституційно врегульованої системи економічних відносин, що забезпечує реалізацію власних і делегованих повноважень, задоволення суспільних потреб та сприяє сталому соціально-економічному розвитку.

В умовах воєнного стану та викликів повоєнного відновлення місцеві фінанси трансформуються з суто бюджетного інструменту у стратегічний механізм забезпечення соціальної стабільності. Зроблено висновок, що сучасна соціальна роль місцевих фінансів полягає у підтримці внутрішньо переміщених осіб, забезпеченні безпеки та сприянні відновленню територіальних громад, що дозволяє розглядати їх як фундаментальний елемент стійкості системи публічних фінансів.

Ключові слова: місцеві фінанси, публічні фінанси, територіальні громади, фінансова стійкість, суспільна роль.

Abstract. The article examines the economic nature of local finance and determines its social role under the transformation of Ukraine's public finance system. The study analyzes the historical evolution of local finance in foreign and domestic contexts, revealing a transition from viewing it as a simple community expenditure estimate to recognizing it as a complex instrument for territorial viability and financial independence. The research highlights that while foreign models followed a gradual path toward autonomy, the Ukrainian experience was marked by a long period of centralization within an administrative-command system, which is currently being overcome through fiscal decentralization.

The paper systematizes academic approaches to defining "local finance" into five categories: system-resource, functional, economic, socio-economic, and legal. This classification demonstrates the multidimensional nature of local finance as both a component of public finance and the foundation of local self-government. The authors propose an updated definition, describing local finance as an institutionally regulated system of economic relations that ensures the implementation of both own and delegated powers, satisfies public needs, and promotes sustainable socio-economic development.

Under the conditions of martial law and the challenges of post-war recovery, local finance is shown to transform from a mere budgetary tool into a strategic mechanism for social stability. The study concludes that the modern social role of local finance is centered on supporting internally displaced persons, ensuring security, and facilitating the recovery of territorial communities, thereby serving as a fundamental element of public finance sustainability.

Keywords: local finance, public finance, territorial communities, financial resilience, social role.

Introduction

The transformation of Ukraine's public finance system, driven by the implementation of fiscal decentralization processes, administrative-territorial reforms, and contemporary socio-economic and security challenges, highlights the need to reconsider the economic nature of local finance and to determine its social role. The strengthening of the financial autonomy of territorial communities is accompanied by increased responsibility of local self-government bodies for the efficiency of public resource management and the quality of public service provision. At the same time, institutional imbalances, uneven financial capacity of communities, dependence of local budgets on intergovernmental transfers, and growing needs for financing territorial recovery necessitate a deeper theoretical understanding of local finance. A review of academic literature on this issue demonstrates the absence of a unified scientific approach to defining the concept of "local finance," which significantly complicates the formation of a holistic vision of its role within the public finance system.

The purpose of this article is to examine the economic nature of local finance and to define its social role under the conditions of transformation of Ukraine's public finance system.

Results

The economic nature of local finance primarily lies in ensuring the financial independence of territorial communities, creating the material basis for the functioning of local self-government bodies, and forming conditions for the provision of public services to meet the needs of the population. Since the accumulation and use of financial resources to satisfy basic social and economic needs of communities take place at the local level, local finance plays a key role in ensuring balanced socio-economic development of territories.

Local finance is a complex economic category due to its dual nature. On the one hand, it is a component of the public finance system; on the other hand, it serves as the financial foundation of local self-government and a tool for implementing local public interests.

The complexity, multidimensionality, and duality of local finance are the result of its long-term transformation influenced by fundamental changes in state structure and intergovernmental fiscal relations.

An analysis of the historical evolution of local finance in foreign and domestic contexts shows a transition from viewing it as a simple “community expenditure estimate” to recognizing it as a complex instrument for ensuring territorial viability and financial independence. Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of conceptual approaches to understanding the nature of local finance in global and Ukrainian practice.

Figure 1 – Evolutionary periodization of conceptual approaches to understanding the essence of local finance in foreign and domestic practice

The historical analysis of local finance development indicates that this process was not linear, as it depended on the political and economic structure of individual countries. In foreign countries, the development of local finance has been gradual and consistent, based on the progressive expansion of financial autonomy at the local level – from financing municipal services to implementing decentralized and integrated public finance models oriented toward long-term socio-economic development.

In contrast, the domestic experience is characterized by a prolonged period of centralization of financial resources within the administrative-command system, which resulted in a dependent model of local finance without real budgetary autonomy. After Ukraine gained independence in the 1990s, the development of local finance acquired an institutional orientation, manifested in the establishment of local budgets, assignment of own-source revenues, and delineation of powers among levels of public authority. The current

stage is characterized by intensified fiscal decentralization and a transition to an integrated public finance model, in which the local level is regarded as an active participant in ensuring financial stability, recovery, and sustainable territorial development. Comparative analysis shows that Ukraine has successfully overcome the period of centralization, and its modern local finance model is developing within the broader European vector, prioritizing a balance between state regulation and financial autonomy of territorial communities.

The identified features of the evolution of local finance in foreign and domestic contexts have led to a diversity of scientific approaches to its interpretation. As a result, Ukrainian academic discourse contains a wide range of definitions requiring systematization. Analysis of scientific and methodological approaches reveals various conceptual emphases, including system-resource, functional, economic, socio-economic, and legal approaches (Table 1).

Table 1 – Systematization of conceptual approaches to understanding the nature of local finance

Author	Definition
V. I. Kravchenko	Local finance is a system for the formation, distribution, and use of monetary and other financial resources to ensure the performance of functions and tasks assigned to local authorities, both own and delegated.
L. K. Voronova	Local finance is a system for the formation, distribution, and expenditure of revenues by territorial communities and local authorities in order to perform the functions and tasks assigned to them.
O. D. Vasylyk	Local finance is a set of forms and methods for creating and using financial resources to ensure the performance by local self-government bodies of the functions assigned to them in the field of economic and social development of the respective territories.
O. R. Romanenko	Local finance is a system for the formation, distribution, and use of financial resources to ensure that local authorities perform the functions and tasks assigned to them, both own and delegated.
V. M. Fedosov, S. I. Yurii et al.	Local finance is a system for the formation, distribution, and use of monetary and other financial resources to ensure the performance of tasks and functions assigned to local authorities.
O. B. Zhykhor, O. P. Kyrylenko	Local finance represents a system of economic relations related to the formation, distribution, and use of financial resources necessary for local self-government bodies to perform the tasks assigned to them.
M. V. Honcharenko	Local finance is a system of economic relations between local self-government bodies, state authorities, individuals, and legal entities related to the distribution and redistribution of a share of the value of gross domestic product created in society in order to meet the population's needs for public goods.
O. O. Suntsova	Local finance is a system for the formation, distribution, and use of monetary and other financial resources to ensure that local authorities perform the functions and tasks assigned to them, both own and delegated.
N. I. Vlasiuk, T. V. Medynska	Local finance is a system for the formation, distribution, and use of financial resources to ensure the performance by local authorities of the functions and tasks assigned to them, both own and delegated by the state.
Yu. V. Chyrychenko, N. P. Kozhalina	Local finance is a set of socio-economic relations related to the formation, distribution, and redistribution of financial resources aimed at solving immediate tasks and performing the functions of local authorities.
O. P. Orliuk	Local finance is a set of relations regulated by the norms of financial law that arise between local self-government bodies and territorial communities, state authorities, enterprises, institutions, and organizations regarding the formation, distribution, and use of funds of local self-government bodies in order to satisfy the public interest of the territorial community and ensure the performance of state functions by local self-government bodies in the process of exercising own and state-delegated powers.

In summary, the modern paradigm of local finance is based on a combination of its resource nature (funds) and social mission (meeting community needs). Most scholars agree that local finance is a key

prerequisite for the financial sustainability of territorial communities, providing the material basis for implementing subsidiarity and decentralization principles.

The overwhelming majority of scholars adhere to the system–resource approach, according to which local finance is defined as a system for the formation, distribution, and use of financial resources required for the performance of the functions and tasks of local self-government bodies. A distinctive feature of this approach is its clear focus on the resource provision of both own and delegated powers of local authorities, which makes it the most suitable for practical application in the field of budget planning and intergovernmental fiscal relations. Representatives of the classical school of finance, including V. M. Fedosov, S. I. Yuriy, O. R. Romanenko, and V. I. Kravchenko, emphasize the triad of “formation, distribution, and use” of financial resources, with an important characteristic being the focus on ensuring the performance of local government functions. In the interpretations proposed by O. O. Suntsova, N. I. Vlasiuk, and T. V. Medynska, the content of the concept becomes more comprehensive and profound, highlighting the dual nature of the powers of local self-government bodies, which combine both their own competences and powers delegated by the state. Of particular importance is the interpretation by L. K. Voronova, who introduces into scholarly discourse an important subject – the territorial community – defining local finance as a system of revenue formation and expenditure carried out specifically by the community and local authorities in order to realize shared interests.

Within the functional–managerial approach, local finance is viewed as an instrument for implementing the economic and social development of the respective territories. In particular, the definition of local finance presented in the works of O. Vasylyk emphasizes the purposeful use of financial resources and strengthens the strategic dimension of local finance in the context of decentralization.

The economic approach to interpreting local finance is represented in the study by M. V. Honcharenko, who emphasizes the macroeconomic nature of local finance, its role in providing public goods at the local level, and considers this concept through the prism of economic relations.

A separate group consists of definitions based on the socio-economic approach, according to which local finance is interpreted as socio-economic relations aimed at solving the immediate tasks of territorial communities. Representatives of this direction, Yu. V. Chyrychenko and N. P. Kozhalina, emphasize the institutional role of local finance as the financial basis for exercising the powers of local authorities within the respective territories.

The legal approach proposed by O. P. Orliuk is comprehensive and combines economic, institutional, and legal aspects, which corresponds to the contemporary conditions of reforming the public finance system. It defines local finance not merely as monetary funds, but as a democratic institution that ensures the implementation of state functions at the local level through the mechanism of self-government. The author goes beyond a purely economic perspective of fund allocation and considers local finance as a set of relations empirically regulated by the norms of financial law, where the concept of the “public interest” of the territorial community becomes central.

Thus, local finance should be considered not only as the resource base of local authorities, but also as an important element of the public finance system that ensures the realization of the interests of territorial communities and the sustainable development of the respective territories. In our view, local finance is an institutionally regulated system of economic relations concerning the formation, distribution, and use of the financial resources of territorial communities, which ensures the implementation of own and delegated powers of local self-government bodies, the satisfaction of public needs of the population, and the achievement of sustainable socio-economic development goals of territories.

An analysis of scientific and methodological literature on public finance in general and local finance in particular confirms that local finance occupies an important place in Ukraine’s public finance system, as it reflects the economic nature of financial relations that arise in the process of ensuring the functioning of territorial communities and implementing public functions at the local level. Given the implementation of decentralization processes in Ukraine, local finance constitutes an autonomous yet institutionally integrated component of public finance, which operates in close interaction with state finance through the system of

intergovernmental fiscal relations, ensuring the redistribution of financial resources in accordance with the powers of different levels of public authority (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Local finances in Ukraine's public finance system

Conclusions

Under the conditions of transformation of Ukraine's public finance system, local finance acquires new social significance. The expansion of the revenue base of local budgets, the transfer of expenditure responsibilities, and the strengthening of the financial accountability of local self-government bodies contribute to enhancing the financial capacity of territorial communities and improving the efficiency of public fund utilization. In the current context, characterized by the challenges of martial law and the prioritization of post-war recovery tasks, local finance serves as an important instrument for ensuring financial resilience, social stability, and sustainable development of territorial communities, which determines its strategic role within the public finance system. It is at the local level that financial resources are concentrated to support internally displaced persons, ensure security, and facilitate territorial recovery, thereby increasing the responsibility of local self-government bodies to the community.

Thus, under contemporary conditions, local finance performs a key social role by combining the functions of social protection, recovery, and long-term territorial development. This transforms its economic nature and defines the place of local finance as one of the fundamental elements of public finance sustainability.

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